

FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT: ROLES OF AUDITING IN SELECTED PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES, SOUTH-SOUTH, GEO-POLITICAL ZONE, NIGERIA.

¹, Akaninyene David AKPAN (PhD student)

², Dr. Commy P. Goddy-Mkpa (Senior Lecturer).

^{1,2} Department of Business Education, Faculty of Vocational Education, Library and Information Science, University of Uyo, Uyo.

Email: phdachieveable45yrs@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

The study was to determine the extent to which auditing has fulfilled quality financial management in seven selected public Universities in South-South. Geo-political zone, Nigeria. Four objectives were set for the study, namely investigating the compliance with audit risk; compliance with audit evidence; compliance with management audit and compliance with cost audit in quality financial management in the selected seven public universities. Correspondingly four research questions and three hypotheses respectively guided the study. The review of related literature was adequately treated based on theoretical framework, conceptual framework and empirical framework. The survey design was adopted for the study. The population of the study was 557 auditors in seven selected Universities of the South-South geo-political zone, Nigeria. The sample size was 233 auditors in the seven selected public Universities. The sample size was determined statistically using "Taro Yamane" formula. The stratified random sampling technique was adopted. A researcher-developed instrument titled: "Financial Management: Roles of Auditing in Selected Public Universities, South-South, Nigeria Questionnaire" (FIPEROPQ) was used for data collection for the study. The research instrument was subjected to face validation by three research experts. The internal consistency of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha reliability method. The researcher and two well-briefed research assistants visited all the selected seven public Universities respectively with the letter of introduction attached to the instrument. Simple Linear Regression statistics was used to test the four null hypotheses, set at 0.05 probability level of significance. Findings of the study reveal that auditors roles determines to a strong extent effective quality financial management in public universities in South-South, Nigeria. The study concluded that internal audit units of Universities should be manned by dedicated, well trained staff responsible for regular financial inspection to ensure compliance with auditing standards. The study recommended among others that public Universities' management should regularly train their audit staff to ensure quality financial management in the educational institutions.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Auditing is an independent evaluation carried out by an auditor in accordance with the established rules and regulations. It is ally of the strategic financial management of an organisation. Auditing therefore provides administrators and financial managers with valuable information and recommendations which help in initiating actions meant to improve the financial performance of organisations. According to Adeniji (2023), “an audit is the independent examination of an expression of opinion on the financial statements of an enterprise by an appointed auditor in pursuance of that appointment and in compliance with any relevant statutory obligation”. It is therefore emphasized that auditor are required for a close inspection of the books of accounts.(Bird, 2017). Cook and Winkle (2018) and Kirkby (2016), posited that “auditing standards is a set of principles and requirements that provide the basis for how an auditor prepares for, performs and reports the results of audits”; while Myees (2023) maintained that auditing standard means a level of auditing quality or excellence established by the tax institute as a norm to be accepted and followed by auditors of published financial statements.

Kirkby (2016) asserted that audit risk is the risk that auditors may give an inappropriate opinion the financial statement. It is the probability that the auditor would draw invalid audit conclusions and therefore express invalid audit opinion. Audit risk focuses the auditors’ attention on factors which are more likely to result in misstatement and it facilitates the use of sampling and the attendant benefits derived there from.

According to Moneke (2018), audit evidence states that the auditor should use assertions for classes of transaction, account balances and presentation and disclosures in sufficient detail to form the basis for the assessment of risks of material misstatement and the design and performance of further audit procedures. The audit evidence is meant to support the company’s claims made in the financial statements and their legal jurisdiction.

According to Banton (2022), management audit is an analysis and assessment of the competencies and capabilities of a company's management in carrying out corporate objectives. The purpose of a management audit is not to appraise individual executive performance but to evaluate the management team in its effectiveness to work in the interests of shareholders, maintain good relations with employees, and uphold reputational standards

Cost audit means the checking and verification of the cost accountancy books, records, statements, reports and other data related to the cost of a product or service being provided by a business unit. Such verification is done by a cost accountant who is appointed by company management, with prior approval from the Central Government, as the cost auditor. Such verification is done not only for the entries made in the cost accounting books but also to see that the various resources are used by the company with maximum efficiency and that the cost of production and cost of sales are kept to the minimum.

Financial management is a subjective measure of how effectively an organization can utilize assets from its primary mode of business and generate funds. It is the process of measuring the results of a business’ policies and operations in monetary terms. Gok and Peker (2017) and Harash (2015) opined that financial management is a measure of how well a firm uses its assets from its primary mode of business to generate returns.

Despite the importance of auditing for accountability, many public Universities in Nigeria are struggling to comply with the standards by their auditors. This lack of compliance has been attributed to a negatively impact on the financial management of these highest tiers of

educational institutions, leading to issues, like misappropriation of funds, embezzlement of funds, inefficiency in resource allocation, and poor accountability to stakeholders.

Hence, this study investigated the extent to which auditing has fulfilled quality financial management in seven selected public Universities in South–South of Nigeria. The objectives of the study include - Compliance with audit risk; Compliance with audit evidence; Compliance with management audit and compliance with cost audit in predicting financial management in selected public universities in South-South, geo-political zone, Nigeria.

Methods and Materials

The study adopted the correlational design; and was carried out in South-South, geo-political zone, Nigeria with seven public universities. Population of this study was 557 auditors in seven public universities, South-South, Nigeria, namely: University of Port Harcourt (UNIPORT), Federal University of Petroleum Resources, Effurun (FUPRE) - Delta, University of Benin (UNIBEN), Federal University, Ikot Abasi; Federal University, Otuoke, University of Uyo (UNIUYO) and University of Calabar (UNICAL). The sample size was 233 auditors in the seven public Universities. The sample size was determined statistically using the “T; Yamane” formula. A stratified random sampling technique was adopted.

A researcher-developed instrument entitled: “Financial Management: Roles of Auditing in Selected Public Universities, South-South, Nigeria Questionnaire” (FIPEROPQ) was used for data collection from the respondents. The instrument was subjected to face validation by three research experts, two from the Department of Business Education (Accounting Unit), Faculty of Vocational Education, Library and Information and one from the Department of Psychological Foundation of Education, Faculty of Education, University of Uyo; and the internal consistency of the instrument was determined using the Cronbach Alpha reliability method. The study also addressed the ethical issues by seeking the consent of the authority concerned in order to achieve the purpose of the study.

Result and Discussion

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: Compliance with audit risk does not significantly predict quality financial management in public universities in South-South, geo-political zone, Nigeria.

Table 1: Simple Linear Regression Analysis for the Compliance with audit risk and quality financial management in public universities in South-South, geo-political zone, Nigeria

	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
	Regression	92.219	1	92.219	4.022	.006	Sig.
1	Residual	5135.628	225	22.927			
	Total	5227.847	226				

Significant @ 0.05 Level

The output in Table 1 reports the calculated F-value of 4.022 with its corresponding p-value of .006 which is less than the .05 level of significant with 1 and 226 degrees of freedom. With this

result, Hence, the result implies that compliance with audit risk significantly predicts quality financial management in public universities in South-South, geo-political zone, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two: Compliance with management audit does not significantly predict quality financial management in public universities in South-South, Nigeria.

Table 2: Simple Linear Regression Analysis for the compliance with management audit and financial performance in public universities in South-South, geo-political zone, Nigeria

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
1 Regression	24.874	1	24.874	1.071	.007 ^b	Sig.
Residual	5202.973	225	23.228			
Total	5227.847	226				

Significant @ 0.05 Level

The output in Table 4.12 reports the calculated F-value of 1.071 with its corresponding p-value of .007 which is less than the .05 level of significant with 1 and 226 degrees of freedom. With this result, the null hypothesis which stated that compliance with management audit does not significantly predict quality financial management in public universities in south-south, Nigeria is rejected. Hence, the result implies that compliance with management audit significantly predicts quality financial management in public universities in South-South, geo-political zone Nigeria.

Hypothesis Three: Compliance with audit evidence does not significantly predict quality financial management in public universities in South-South, geo-political zone Nigeria.

Table 3: Simple Linear Regression Analysis for the Compliance with audit evidence and financial performance in public universities in South-South, geo-political zone, Nigeria.

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
1 Regression	.678	1	.678	.029	.012	Sig.
Residual	5227.170	225	23.336			
Total	5227.847	226				

Significant @ 0.05 Level

The output in Table 4.13 reports the calculated F-value of .029 with its corresponding p-value of .012 which is less than the .05 level of significant with 1 and 226 degrees of freedom. With this result, the null hypothesis which stated that compliance with audit evidence does not significantly predict quality financial management in public universities in south-south, Nigeria

is rejected. Hence, the result implies that compliance with audit evidence significantly predicts quality financial management in public universities in South-South, geo-political zone, Nigeria

Hypothesis Four: Compliance with cost audit does not significantly predict quality financial management in public universities in South-South, geo-political zone Nigeria.

Table 4 Simple Linear Regression Analysis for the Compliance with cost audit and quality financial management in public universities in south-south, geo-political zone, Nigeria

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Regression	72.441	1	72.441	3.148	.001	Sig
Residual	5155.406	225	23.015			
Total	5227.847	226				

Significant @ 0.05 Level

The output in Table 4.14 reports the calculated F-value of 3.148 with its corresponding p-value of .001 which is less than the .05 level of significant with 1 and 226 degrees of freedom. With this result, the null hypothesis which stated that compliance with cost audit does not significantly predict quality financial management in public universities in South-South, geo-political zone, Nigeria is rejected. Hence, the result implies that compliance with cost audit significantly predicts quality financial management in public universities in South-South, geo-political zone, Nigeria.

The findings revealed the following:

- i. Compliance with audit risk determines to a strong extent predicted quality financial management in public universities in South-South, geo-political zone, Nigeria.
- ii. Compliance with audit evidence determines to a strong extent predicted quality financial management in public universities in south-south, Nigeria.
- iii. Compliance with management audit determines to a strong extent predicted quality financial management in public universities in South-South, geo-political zone, Nigeria.
- iv. Compliance with cost audit determines to a strong extent predicted quality financial management in public universities in South-South, geo-political zone, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

Compliance with audit risk and financial performance in public universities in South-South, geo-political zone, Nigeria

The finding from research question four revealed that compliance with audit risk determines to a strong extent financial performance in public universities in South-South, geo-political zone, Nigeria. The corresponding null hypothesis shows that compliance with audit risk significantly

predicts financial performance in public universities in south-south, geo-political zone, Nigeria. This finding suggests that audit risk makes an auditor not to detect errors or fraud while examining the financial statements of a client hence auditors in a way could increase the number of audit procedures in order to reduce the level of audit risk. The present finding is in line with the finding of Olagunju *et al.* (2023) who asserted the need to prioritize, segregate duties and enhance mechanisms for employing and sustaining internal audit services to improve resource management in public tertiary institutions. The present finding also *parripasua* with the findings of DeSimone and Rich (2020) who elucidated that large-scale quantitative analysis of IAF offers valuable insights aiming to enhance financial reporting quality and grant outcomes, as well as for external stakeholders assessing institutional resource stewardship. The present findings are in line with the findings of Abbass and Aleqab (2013) who ascertained that since audit risk is the danger of financial statements being significantly inaccurate auditor could perform inquires and check on the general ledger and the relevant documents during an audit then auditors could demand that the journal entries be corrected.

All these discussions tilted to the fact that in reducing risk, auditors could conduct regular risk evaluations, possess risk management policy and increase internal audit staff to ensure broader audit coverage and timely execution of audit activities.

Compliance with audit evidence determines to a strong extent financial performance in public universities in South-South, geo-political zone, Nigeria

The finding from research question five revealed that compliance with audit evidence determines to a strong extent financial performance in public universities in South-South, geo-political zone, Nigeria. The corresponding Hypothesis shows that compliance with management audit significantly predicts financial performance in public universities in south-south, geo-political zone, Nigeria. The findings suggest that auditors obtain sufficient and appropriate evidence that enables them to arrive at a conclusion that supports their opinion. The present finding is in line with the finding of Effiok and Bassey (2015) who hold that the integration of robust audit evidence, and effective audit committees leads to more accurate financial disclosures and improves which improves the overall financial position of organizations. The findings are in consonance with the findings of Ehumadu (2017) asserted that auditing evidence ensures information collected for review of a company's financial transactions, internal control practices and other items necessary for the certification of financial statements by an auditor or certified public accountant is expedient. This finding of the present study is in line with the findings of Okonkwo and Ile, (2019) who asserted that the management of tertiary educational institutions should urgently emboss institution names on all assets and regularly update fixed asset registers to protect against pilfering and unauthorized use. These measures are aimed at enhancing the safeguarding and proper management of assets in financial reporting.

Compliance with management audit and financial performance in public universities in South-South, geo-political zone, Nigeria

The finding from research question six revealed that compliance with management audit determines to a strong extent financial performance in public universities in South-South, geo-political zone, Nigeria. The corresponding null hypothesis shows that compliance with audit evidence significantly predicts financial performance in public universities in south-south, Nigeria. The findings of the present study suggest that management audit is a form of appraisal of the total performance of the management by means of an objective and comprehensive examination of the organisation structure. The present finding is in line

with the finding of Nwosu *et al.* (2022) investigating the impact of management audits on financial accountability in Nigerian Colleges of Education and asserted for an improvement in financial accountability as a result of management audits.

The present finding is in line with the findings of Ebirien and Umoffong (2018) who revealed that management audit establishes the relationship between internal audit function and financial performance in terms of all activities set out by management. This finding indicated profiling in the internal audit unit with the appropriate number of staff and professional member of accountancy body for ethical justification, the present finding is also in line with the assertion postulated Ziniyel *et al.* (2018) that management audit underscores the relevance of internal auditors' qualifications and experience in influencing financial outcomes positively. Hence, the independence of the internal audit function and its role in management assistance emerged as critical factors contributing to financial performance within the university. The present finding is in line with the finding of Okoye and Ofoegbu (2018) who asserted that management audit offers actionable insights for policymakers and educational administrators seeking to optimize financial management strategies. This present finding also calls for the widespread adoption of management audits to further strengthen financial accountability practices and governance. Hence a contribution to valuable insights for the practical application and benefits of management audits in educational financial management contexts.

Compliance with cost audit and financial performance in public universities South-South, Geo-political zone, Nigeria

The finding from research question seven revealed that compliance with cost audit determines a strong extent of financial performance in public universities South-South, geo-political zone, Nigeria. The corresponding null hypothesis also shows that compliance with cost audit significantly predicts quality financial management in public universities in south-south, geo-political zone, Nigeria. The findings of the present study suggest that cost audit is mainly a correctness of cost accounts, adherence to the cost accounting principles, plans, procedures, preventive measures, guide for management policy and decisions in addition to bringing the barometer of performance in all ramifications. The present finding is in line with the assertion of Ogundipe (2019) who asserted that cost audits as a tool for financial improvement have the efficacy to enhance the quality financial management of organizations or institutions hence, the implementation of cost audits to substantially prioritize cost audit practices to bolster financial performance. The present finding is congruence with the finding of Larasati *et al.* (2019) who noted that the involvement of an independent commissioner as an audit committee member strengthens the relationship between the Risk Management Committee (RMC) and audit fees.

The present findings are congruence with the findings of Ahmed (2018) who asserted that cost audit enhances cost control within an institution. Hence its effectiveness for improving cost control measures within an institution. The overall finding demonstrates the presence of insights that provide valuable contributions to regulatory bodies by offering empirical evidence on the interplay between board governance structures and audit pricing in non-financial industries. Hence the underscore the importance of independent audit committees in enhancing the quality of financial oversight and risk management, thereby influencing audit practices and costs.

Conclusion

The study indicated that auditors in the universities presented responsible roles in quality auditing for better budget management, transparent financial reporting, and effective use of resources Compliance with auditing standards by the auditors have helped the universities

identify and mitigate financial risks. That has may led to increased trust from stakeholders, including government, professional bodies, students, and donors.

Recommendations

The study offered the following recommendations:

- i. University managers should have dedicated, well-trained internal auditors responsible for regular financial oversight and ensuring compliance with auditing standards.
- ii. The university management should conduct frequent internal audits, especially in high-risk areas like procurement, payroll, and research funding, to ensure adherence to financial controls.
- iii. The university management should ensure continuous training and professional development for internal audit staff to stay up-to-date with evolving auditing standards and technologies.
- iv. The university management should implement clear and standardized financial policies that align with national and international auditing standards (such as International Standards on Auditing).
- v. The university administration should establish a monitoring and evaluation framework to regularly assess the effectiveness of financial policies and how well they align with auditing standards.
- vi. Universities should publicly disclose their financial statements and audit reports to promote transparency and build trust with stakeholders, including students, staff, government bodies, and donors.
- vii. University management should regularly engage reputable external audit firms to independently assess financial performance and adherence to auditing standards.
- viii. Ensure that audit recommendations made by external auditors are effectively implemented and regularly followed up to improve financial processes and close any gaps in compliance.
- ix. Work closely with government audit bodies to ensure that university financial management aligns with public sector auditing requirements.
- x. Universities should create a risk management framework that identifies financial risks and integrates those into the auditing process in order to ensure proactive identification of issues that could affect financial performance.

REFERENCES

- Abbass, D. A., and Aleqab, M. M. (2013). Internal Auditor's Characteristics and Audit Fees: Evidence from Egyptian Firms. *International Business Research*, 6, 67-80.
- Adeniji, A. A. (2023). *Auditing and Assurance Services* (2nded.). Value Analysis Consult, Lagos.
- Banton, C. (2022). Management Audit: definition, how it works and what it addresses. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/m/management-audit.asp#>. Retrieved May 11, 2024.
- Bird, R. M. (2017). Auditing and accountability: The role of book inspections in financial governance. *Journal of Accounting in Finance*, 12(3): 45 - 62.

- DeSimone, S., and Rich, K. (2020). Determinants and consequences of internal audit functions within colleges and universities. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 35(8).
- Ebirien, G. I., and Umoffong, N. J. (2018). Internal Audit Function and management support in Nigerian Public Tertiary Institutions. *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 8(2), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajeba/2018/43725>
- Effiok, S. O., and Bassey, B. E. (2015). Information technology, audit evidence and financial performance of an organization. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 7(3).
- Ehumadu, F. (2017). Effectiveness of internal audit as an instrument of internal control in an organization. A study of manufacturing firms in Enugu State. Project supervised in Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT), Enugu.
- Gok, O and Peker, S. (2017). Understanding the links among innovation performance, market performance and financial performance, *Review of Managerial Science*, 11(3): 605-631.
- Harash, E. (2015). The role environmental uncertainty in the link between accounting information system and performance small and medium enterprises in Iraq. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 15(2): 23-35.
- Kabir, U. (2012). Internal control systems and corporate survival in the Nigerian banking industry. *Journal of Auditing*, 8(11): 38-41.
- Kirkby, D. (2016). *One hundred questions in auditing with suggested answer for Accountancy*. 16th Edition. Pergamon Press.
- Larasati, D. A., Ratri, M. C., Nasih, M., and Harymawan, I. (2019). Independent Audit Committee, Risk Management Committee, and audit fees. *Cogent Business and Management*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2019.1707042>
- Moneke, G. O. (2018). *Budgetary planning for capital projects and construction contract planning*. 1st Edition. Nigerian Institute of Quantity Surveyors.
- Myees, J. H. (2023). *Auditing cases*. 1st Edition: Northwestern University Press.
- Nwosu, S. N., Aguwamba, S. M., and Akwawa, U. A. (2022). Internal auditors and corporate governance in Nigerian Universities. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention (IJBMI)*, 11(4).
- Ogundipe, K. (2019). Effect of cost audit on financial performance of tertiary institutions in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Management*, 2(2), 126-137.
- Okonkwo, M. U., and Ile, C. M. (2019). Extent of implementation of auditing guidelines for assets in financial reporting in tertiary educational institutions in south east, Nigeria. *European Journal of Education Studies*, 6(9).
- Okoye, E. I. and Ofoegbu, G. N. (2018). The relevance of accounting and auditing standards in corporate financial reporting in Nigeria. Emphasis on compliance.

- Olagunju, A., Shittu, R. M., and Nwikpasi, N. N. (2023). Internal audit and management of fund in government owned Universities in Osun State. *Global Journal of Accounting*, 9(1).
- Ziniyel, D., Otoo, I. C., & Andzie, T. A. (2018). Effect Of Internal Audit Practices On Financial Management. *European Journal of Business, Economics and Accountancy*, 6(3).